

POLITICAL SCIENCES

ETHNO-POLITICAL CONTEXTS IN THE PROGRAMS OF POLITICAL PARTIES OF KAZAKHSTAN AND CHINA

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Abstract

The role of political parties in multi-ethnic states is quite complex, as they should be focused not only on political governance at the level of the state as a whole, but also on promoting national unity in inter-ethnic relations, forming tolerant cooperation and interaction between different ethnic groups. One of the tasks of political parties in multi-ethnic states is to integrate different social interests and ensure that all ethnic groups have a voice and are represented in the decision-making process at the national level. In addition, political parties can act as mediators and promoters of inter-ethnic harmony by easing inter-ethnic tensions through inclusive policies and implementing preventive measures to resolve potential ethnic conflicts. This article aims to take the operation and development of political parties in multi-ethnic countries such as Kazakhstan and China as examples to study the role of political parties and to study cases from the practice of their activities in maintaining national stability, promoting social harmony, and protecting the interests of small ethnic groups. The research paper pointed out that the policies developed and implemented by political parties in multicultural countries in support of the cultures of different ethnic groups, the protection and promotion of the languages, religions, traditions and cultural identities of different ethnic groups, comply with the UN standards and principles on these issues. However, as shown by the political and SWOT analysis of the statutory and program documents of the political parties in the countries studied, there are problems. Certainly, political parties are making efforts to ensure equal opportunities and access for all ethnic groups to the economy, education, employment and so on, in order to promote the creation of a fair and inclusive society, while ensuring the civil rights of minority ethnic groups, or as it is called in international legal literature "national minorities".

Keywords: political parties, multi-ethnicity, ethnic culture, ethnic conflict, fractures in politics, programmatic attitudes and orientations.

Introduction

Political parties play an important role in the governance of a country, and their role encompasses several aspects. First, political parties, as political representatives, represent the interests of voters and social groups in their program documents, and their authority is transferred to them through the electoral process. Second, through party programs and policy documents, they propose specific policies to guide national development in the economic, social and cultural fields. In a multiparty system, the existence of different political parties provides mutual checks and balances. Political parties, as an intermediary between citizens and the state, also provide an opportunity for the general public to participate in the political process.

In multi-ethnic states, political parties can represent different ethnic and cultural groups and reflect the pluralism of society by including members from different backgrounds. This helps make the political system more social and representative to meet the needs and interests of different ethnic groups. Multi-ethnic states often face tensions and potential conflicts between different groups. Political parties can support social cohesion by establishing a common political agenda and values that promote socio-political stability and reduce ethnic conflict.

Political parties are a central component of a democratic system through which representatives of all ethnic groups can participate in the decision-making process. This helps ensure that the views of different social groups are adequately heard and prevents the rights and interests of minorities from being ignored. In general, political parties play a key role in governing multi-ethnic states to promote social harmony, stability and sustainable development.

However, this requires that political parties be inclusive, representative and impartial so that all ethnic groups can participate in and be treated fairly in the political process. In this regard, we can consider two representative countries, Kazakhstan and China, which are characterized by rich multiculturalism within the country, where different ethnic groups interact with each other, creating a diverse ethno-cultural landscape.

Literature Review

Ethnicity has always been an important area of academic research. The fact that today there are more than 7,000 ethnic groups in the world, but just more than 190 nation-states. Seven major ethnic groups, including those living in the countries under study, do not have their own statehood, but have ambitions to create one. Among them are Uighurs, Kurds, Palestinians, Tibetans, Catalans, and Sikhs, most of whom live in both

Kazakhstan and China. Therefore, national models of ethno-politics should take into account the peculiarities of multi-ethnicity in the programs and charters of political parties.

It is undoubted that the creation of a multinational state meant that various ethnic groups were within the framework of the national state system. However, the obvious heterogeneity of ethnic groups and clear boundaries between them still remain, which causes secondary tension between the nation and the state (Ren Qiang, 2016). This reality challenges the multi-ethnic state system. The presence of such contradictions can at any moment detach ethnic groups from the state, which will directly affect the functioning of the multinational state system and stability in society. In this context, inter-ethnic political integration is particularly important, utilizing mechanisms and means to bridge the gap between different ethnic groups, and between ethnic groups and the state in order to maintain stability, social harmony and sustainable development of the country.

There are different types of political parties in multi-ethnic states, and the role of different parties in inter-ethnic political integration is not the same. There are two main types of the role of political parties in interethnic political integration: one directly in inter-ethnic political integration, the other is indirectly. This is mainly achieved in three ways: firstly, political parties achieve interethnic political integration through the organization and use of state power; Secondly, political parties promote and protect the policy of interethnic political integration through the form of state power; Thirdly, political parties use state power to promote national construction (Zhou Ping, 2021). All three methods are used by political parties in order to promote their values and policies of interethnic political integration, and to convey the necessity of implementing national political integration to national political elites that exercise national power.

The governance system in China is characterized by a high degree of centralization. The state has strong governing bodies and control mechanisms in all political, economic and social spheres (Zhang Yunyi, 2022). The Communist Party of China (CPC) and the government play a central role in the governance of the state. The modern Chinese approach to interethnic political integration is an authoritarian-institutional model that relies on the rule of law system to integrate contradictions between ethnic groups and the state (Chang Shixiang & Han Zhengming, 2011). Analyzing the need for authority and institutions, specific ways of inter-ethnic political integration and stability are proposed.

From the point of view of Marxist ethnic theory, the CPC began the study of inter-ethnic political integration at the very beginning of its activities. The CPC applies organizational, institutional and political logic to inter-ethnic politics by fully mobilizing ethnic minority representatives and establishing mechanisms for their participation and integration into the Party, establishes a system of regional ethnic autonomy based on interaction between the ethnic group and the State, that is, recognizing and respecting differences among ethnic

groups, formulating and implementing policies for the benefit of ethnic minorities (Xia Dongmin & Hou Qiang, 2015). Currently, the CPC is a comprehensive, consistent, long-term and direct ruling party in China (Zhang Huilong, 2014). These guiding characteristics have defined the CPC's leadership position in inter-ethnic political integration and influenced the implementation of inter-ethnic policies.

The consistent reforms of the state nation-building in the period of Kazakhstan's independence allowed to ensure the strengthening of the basic foundations of statehood, define domestic and foreign policy, develop strategic goals and build a parity practice of interaction between the state and society. Today, it is becoming increasingly clear that the processes of globalization and the processes of universalization and standardization that are arising from them are inevitable for all countries who want to be among the developed ones. At the same time, there is also an understanding that a natural consequence of globalization is the crisis of national identities, which as a natural reaction to uncertainty gives birth to the growth of national consciousness, and, accordingly, the interest and revival of national culture (Ivanov V.N., 2014). Kazakhstan was no exception in this regard. When considering this phenomenon, we can turn to the interpretation of scientists who note that the national culture is the basic element of the organization, and not only provides resistance to external cultural influences, but also has the ability to change them under its influence. Whereas, based on the philosophical approach, it is in self-awareness that the nation determines its fundamental interests, common ideals, its attitude to other nations and states. In this case, national identity is considered as the basic value of national culture (Zykin A.V. & Tufanov A.O., 2015).

Interaction between ethno-cultural associations and civil society institutions, especially in multi-ethnic states, is an integral part of the historical development of virtually all peoples of the world. There are many examples from history when peoples tried to live in isolation, which deprived them of the possibility of further development and, in the end, led to lagging behind other peoples and countries.

Kazakhstan has always developed on the path of openness to the intercultural dialogue. Over several centuries of residence of various ethnic groups on Kazakh land, a rich experience of socio-humanitarian and interethnic cooperation has been accumulated.

Historically, the relations formed on the expanses of the Great Steppe tend to preserve the traditions of cohabitation, which was the basis for the formation of the culture of interethnic relations. To consider inter-ethnic relations in isolation from the historical context, does not allow to fully and completely study this problematic.

Unlike centralized governance in China, governance in Kazakhstan is more decentralized, moving towards a market economy and democratic politics. The search for ways to manage interethnic relations in Kazakhstan began in the Soviet period. From studies on the Soviet period, it follows that the Communist Party of the Soviet Union (CPSU) was the key and the center of interethnic political integration in the Soviet Union,

and that the CPSU carried out interethnic political integration in three main ways. The first was the high concentration of power in the hands of individuals; the second was control over society as a whole; and the third was control over ethnic territories (Chang Shiyin, 2012). The CPSU, in the name of the unity and security of The Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR), applied force to clean and persecute the so-called "national dissidents." The mechanism of violent integration and compulsory fusion reflects the CPSU's strong bureaucracy and blindly pursuit for homogeneity (Zhu Bibo, 2011). Since political parties are the core of interethnic political integration, they play a fundamental role. Thus, we can say that inter-ethnic political integration in the USSR was made possible by political parties, and it was also defeated by political parties (Zhou Ping, 2011).

Since the collapse of the Soviet Union, Kazakhstan, being at the center of Eurasia, has been quite exemplary in terms of multi-ethnic governance. Inter-ethnic political integration in Kazakhstan is based on the experience of the Soviet period, and the model of inter-ethnic political integration is expressed mainly in the harmonious coexistence of numerous ethnic groups (according to the National Bureau of Statistics, there are 126 different ethnic groups in Kazakhstan), which found themselves in Kazakhstan under the influence of various migration and ethno-migration processes, including those related to forced resettlement, deportation, mass political repressions in the early and mid-20th century. Kazakhstan is a presidential republic with a relatively centralized political system. There are 7 major registered political parties in Kazakhstan, but in general the political scene is dominated by the president and the ruling party. (Asylov K.J., 2018) The government focused on maintaining harmonious relations between ethnic groups and took measures to promote the policy of multiculturalism and multilingualism. At the political level, the government of Kazakhstan advocates a model of multi-ethnic integration. At the socio-political level, the Kazakhstan's model of social concord and national unity is valid (Nazarbayev N.A., 2003), which emphasizes mutual respect and cooperation between various ethnic groups. However, some ethnic communities may feel unequal in terms of political participation and resource allocation, and some feel marginalized in terms of political life. This may be due to the concentration of power in the central government and the underrepresentation at the local government level.

Case and Methodology

Efforts and Challenges in Building Ethnic Relations in China and Kazakhstan

Kazakhstan and China are countries with a rich and diverse ethnic composition. Due to geographical, historical and cultural differences, both countries have a number of unique features in the management of multi-ethnic states. But both Kazakhstan and China strive to preserve the harmonious coexistence of multi-ethnic states and promote the development and prosperity of individual ethnic groups using politics and institutions.

In China and Kazakhstan, political parties are the main participants in the country's political life and have a far-reaching influence on public policy and political system. The CPC occupies a dominant position in Chinese politics and plays a decisive role in the development and implementation of the country's policy. The CPC is the only ruling party of China and has the supreme power in the country since the founding of the country in 1949. The leading position of the CPC is one of the fundamental features of the Chinese political system. Through its organizations at all levels of government and society, the CPC participates in and leads national and local issues, including economic development, social management and cultural construction. The CPC attached great importance to the issue of ethnicity in light of the basic national conditions - a unified multi-ethnic country. In 1957, Mao Zedong profoundly remarked that "the unity of the country, the unity of the people and the unity of all nationalities in the country are the basic guarantees for the victory of the CPC's cause" (Mao Zedong, 1957). Hu Jintao pointed out that "the unification of the motherland is the highest interest of the people of all ethnic groups, and national unity is an important guarantee of the unification of the motherland" (Hu Jintao, 2009). The CPC, as the only legitimate ruling party, plays a central leadership, organizational and coordinating role in building multi-ethnic relations in China. The Chinese Government, under the leadership of the CPC, develops and implements ethnic policies, including policies of national unity and regional ethnic autonomy, provides legal and political guarantees for the harmonious coexistence of various ethnic groups.

In China live 56 ethnic groups, among which the Han Chinese are the most numerous, and the remaining 55 are known as ethnic minorities (2009). The main purpose of establishing multi-ethnic relations in China is to promote the unity, harmony and development of all ethnic groups, ensure equal rights and their national identity. The multinational relations of China can be reflected in the fact that compliance with the principle of ethnic equality, all ethnic groups enjoy equal rights and status in political, economic, cultural and no one ethnic group being superior to another (2021); respect for ethnic identity, respect and protection of cultural traditions, languages and writing, religious beliefs and other characteristics of all ethnic groups; the establishment of autonomous minority areas, these autonomous regions have a certain degree of self-government power and independently manage their economic, cultural, educational and other affairs (Peng Xunwen & Wang Meng, 2017); the development of ethnic solidarity education, promotion of mutual understanding, respect and friendly exchanges between ethnic groups (Zhu Qian, 2016); encouraging exchange and cooperation among all ethnic groups, promoting joint participation of all ethnic groups in nation-building and development.

Kazakhstan is a multi-ethnic country with a much higher ethnic composition than China, and its major ethnic groups include Kazakhs, Russians, Uzbeks, Ukrainians and others (Schatz, E., 2000). As the ruling party of Kazakhstan, AMANAT strives to develop and

promote policies favorable to national unity and pluralistic coexistence. These policies are aimed at promoting harmonious coexistence among ethnic groups and protecting their rights and cultural heritage. Kazakhstan's approach and strategy to building multi-ethnic relations are different from China's, but they are also aimed at promoting unity, harmony and development of various ethnic groups. The formation and development of inter-ethnic relations in Kazakhstan is characterized by the fact that the Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan

gives equal rights to ethnic groups in political, economic, social and cultural spheres, and guarantees all ethnic groups freedom of religion and cultural traditions (Constitution, 1993). Kazakhstan pursues an ethnic policy that includes the protection of linguistic and written rights of ethnic groups, the preservation of cultural traditions and customs, and promoting the economic development of all ethnic groups. Particular attention is paid to the cultural exchange between ethnic groups, education in the spirit of national unity and the formation of national identity.

Table 1

Comparative analysis of the ethnic composition of Kazakhstan and China

	Kazakhstan	China
Ethnic composition	<p>Kazakhs are the main ethnic group in Kazakhstan and make up the majority of the total population. Other major ethnic groups include Russians, Uzbeks, Ukrainians and others.</p> <p>According to the data of the Bureau of National Statistics the ethnic composition at the beginning of 2023:</p> <p>Kazakhs - (70.7%) Russians - (15.2%) Uzbeks - (3.3%) (Bureau of National Statistics, 2023).</p>	<p>The Han Chinese are the main ethnic group in China, making up the vast majority of the total population. There are also 55 ethnic minorities in China, such as Uighurs, Tibetans, Mongols and Hui. According to the seventh national census, as of 2020, the total number of ethnic minorities in China was about 125 million people, or 8.89 percent of the total population of the country. The Han population is 91.11 percent, which makes it the most populous ethnic group (National Bureau of Statistics, 2021).</p>
Language	<p>The Kazakh language is the state language. In state organizations and local governments, Russian language is officially used along with Kazakh. The state takes care of creating conditions for the study and development of languages of the people of Kazakhstan.</p>	<p>Chinese (Mandarin) is the official language, ethnic minorities in different regions also use local languages such as Uighur, Tibetan and Mongolian languages.</p>
Religion	<p>Islam is the main religion. The state encourages religious tolerance and respects all religions.</p>	<p>In China, there are many religious beliefs, including Buddhism, Taoism, Islam and Christianity. The state advocates religious tolerance, but at the same time pursues a strict policy of religious management.</p>
Ethnic compactness	<p>Kazakhs mostly live in the southern and south-eastern regions of Kazakhstan, including Almaty, Turkestan, Kyzylorda, Zhetysu and Zhambyl areas, and the cities of Almaty and Shymkent.</p> <p>Russians are concentrated in the northern and north-western areas of Kazakhstan, such as the capital Astana, Karaganda, North Kazakhstan, Kostanay and Pavlodar regions.</p> <p>Uzbeks live in the southern and south-western areas of Kazakhstan, such as the South Kazakhstan, Turkestan and Almaty regions.</p> <p>Ukrainians mainly live in the northern and western regions of Kazakhstan, including Akmola, Pavlodar, Karaganda and Kostanay regions (Bureau of National Statistics of Kazakhstan, 2023).</p>	<p>China's ethnic minorities mainly live in "minority autonomous regions" or "ethnic minority areas" in the western, southern and northern regions.</p> <p>Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region is located in the northwestern part of China and is mainly inhabited by Uyghurs, Kazakhs, Kyrgyz, Uzbeks and other ethnic minorities.</p> <p>The Tibet Autonomous Region is located on a high plateau in southwestern China. It is home to Tibetans as well as other ethnic groups such as Han, Menba, Hui and Naxi.</p> <p>Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region is located in the northern part of China and is mainly inhabited by Mongols, as well as Han, Daur and others.</p> <p>Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region - in the southern part of China, where are inhabited by Zhuang, Han, Yao, Miao, Dong, Mulao, Maonan, Hui, Jing, Yi, Shui, Gelao.</p> <p>Ningxia Hui Autonomous Region is located in the northwest of China, home to Hui, Uyghur, Dongxiang, Kazakh, and Salar (Yuan Hong, 2024).</p>

Culture and traditions	Kazakhstan has a rich cultural heritage, combining traditions of different ethnic groups, including music, dance, crafts and cuisine.	China has an ancient history and rich cultural traditions, and each ethnic group has unique cultural characteristics, including food, language, clothing, customs and celebrations.
Government form	Kazakhstan is a unitary State with a presidential form of government. Kazakhstan claims to be a democratic, secular, legal and social State the highest values of which are the human being, his or her life, rights and freedoms.	China is a socialist state with a unitary system, the ruling party is the Communist Party of China (CPC). The state solves the problem of multi-ethnic relations through the system of national autonomies.
Political party system	Multi-party system	The system of multi-party cooperation and political consultation under the leadership of the Communist Party of China (China's State Council Information Office, 2021)
Ruling Party	AMANAT	The Communist Party of China
The other major political parties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Democratic Party of Kazakhstan "Aq Jol"</i> • <i>The People's Party of Kazakhstan,</i> • <i>Auyl People's Patriotic Democratic Party,</i> • <i>The National Social Democratic Party,</i> • <i>Baytaq party,</i> • <i>Respublica party. (Central Election Commission, 2024)</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The Revolutionary Committee of the Chinese Kuomintang,</i> • <i>China Democratic League,</i> • <i>China National Democratic Construction Association,</i> • <i>Chinese Peasants' and Workers' Democratic Party,</i> • <i>China Zhi Gong Party,</i> • <i>China Association for Promoting Democracy,</i> • <i>Jiusan Society,</i> • <i>Taiwan Democratic Self-Government League.</i>

Despite years of efforts by the ruling party to maintain ethnic unity, there are still some problems in inter-ethnic relations in China.

First, economic inequality. The relative economic backwardness of some ethnic minority regions and the obvious economic gap with developed regions in the east of the country may lead to economic inequality between different ethnic groups, exacerbating discontent and conflicts between ethnic groups (People's Political Consultative Conference, 2010).

Second, cultural identity and inheritance. Some ethnic minorities face problems of cultural identity and inheritance, and some traditional cultures and languages are in danger of being lost due to modernization and urbanization, which can lead to an ethnic identity crisis. In particular, some small minorities face greater challenges in this regard (Chao Ke & Pan Yuefei, 2016).

Third, conflicts based on religion and belief. Although China respects freedom of religion and belief, there are still some tensions between religion and politics and society, some religious beliefs are contrary to national policies or social values, which may lead to religious strife between ethnic groups.

Kazakhstan, as a multi-ethnic country, adheres to the basic principles and standards of the UN, taking into account the turbulence in the world arena, socio-economic problems face a number of challenges in establishing harmonious inter-ethnic relations.

First, national identity and integration. Despite the fact that Kazakhstan in its policy claims the strengthening of social harmony and national unity as a priority and strategic resource, some ethnic communities may face problems of identification with the dominant ethnic group, the Kazakhs, and there may not be

enough strong consensus on national identity, which can lead to instability in society (Kabaziev M.S., 2022).

Second, economic inequality. The relative economic backwardness of some regions and the obvious economic gap with large urban areas can lead to economic inequality between ethnic groups, increasing social unrest and tension (Analytical Center, 2024).

Third, language policy and cultural preservation. Despite the government's multilingualism policy, the indigenous languages and cultures of some ethnic regions are at risk of being marginalized.

Fourth, political representation and distribution of power. Ethnic groups with small populations may be underrepresented and under-participated in political power structures, and uneven distribution of political power may lead to underrepresentation of the political aspirations of some ethnic groups and increased inter-ethnic tensions.

Fifth, geopolitical contradictions. Kazakhstan occupies an important geopolitical position, and in certain areas there may be ethno-geopolitical contradictions with neighboring countries, such as Russia, China, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan and other neighboring countries, which may affect ethnic relations within the country and cross-country problems.

The ruling parties of China and Kazakhstan pay great attention in their activities to maintaining peaceful, stable and sustainable national development. To achieve this, the ruling parties of China and Kazakhstan are taking a number of measures in the field of managing and coordinating the sphere of interethnic relations, ensuring that all ethnic groups are involved in political decision-making at the highest level. Therefore, parties and their strategies in multi-ethnic states play a key role in maintaining stability and consolidation of society.

The role of political parties in strengthening inter-ethnic harmony

The role and historical efforts of the CPC and AMANAT parties in building democratic inter-ethnic relations are undeniable. Since China's reforms, the CPC is committed to promoting the economic and social development of ethnic minority areas and intensifying efforts to combat poverty and improve living standards and prosperity.

The AMANAT party is committed to promoting economic development, improving living standards, based on the principles of “unity in diversity”, “we are different, we are equal”, and the formation of a public institutional framework to strengthen state ethno-politics. And here, ethno-cultural associations, of which there are more than 1000 in Kazakhstan (The Consulate General, 2021) including members of political parties, through their programs and projects participate in strengthening solidarity.

Table 2

Comparative analysis of program documents and attitudes of political parties of Kazakhstan and China

	AMANAT	The Communist Party of China (CPC)
Theory of nationalities	<p>As the leader of the ruling party, the first president Nazarbayev's comes down to three aspects.</p> <p>Firstly, Kazakhstan is a multi-ethnic state, there is no “new historical community of people”, and the problem of ethnicity exceeds the problem of class (Wei Liangtao, 1997). He made a strict distinction between the use of two terms: “Kazakh” and “Kazakhstani”. The first denotes ethnicity, the second - national.</p> <p>Secondly, “the preservation of inter-ethnic harmony on the basis of equal rights of all Kazakhstanis is a fundamental principle of state policy - the first condition for political stability”. “No more big brothers and little brothers!” (Nazarbayev N.A., 1996).</p> <p>Thirdly, democratic and legal methods are used to resolve emerging ethnic problems and conflicts. “There should be no attempts to suppress objective contradictions. Our strategy should be to pursue a policy of preventing contradictions from escalating into bloody conflicts.” (Nazarbayev N.A., 1996).</p> <p>A practical ethnic development strategy provides a direction for building multi-ethnic relations in the country.</p> <p>All ethnic groups have an extremely high civil, legal and social status. Their representatives do not act as national minorities, but are considered as citizens of the united nation of Kazakhstan with full rights.</p>	<p>In the White Paper “China's Ethnic Policy and the Common Prosperity and Development of All Ethnic Groups,” the CPC states that “although the formation and development of China's ethnic groups have occurred in different ways, the common direction is to develop a unified multi-ethnic state and unite into a unified and strong Chinese nation.” (Sun Qingyou, 2010).</p> <p>“The model of pluralism and unity of the Chinese nation is that unity contains pluralism and pluralism makes up unity; unity is the main line and direction, pluralism is the element and driving force. The relationship between the Chinese nation and various nationalities is the relationship between a big family and its members, the relationship between different nationalities is the relationship between different members of a big family” - Xi Jinping (Wang Zhengwei, 2014).</p> <p>All ethnic groups are equal, regardless of population size, history and level of development. China's ethnic problems can be gradually resolved only within the framework of the common cause of building socialism with Chinese characteristics and realizing the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation.</p> <p>The state creates increasingly favorable opportunities and conditions for the development of ethnic minorities and protects the legitimate rights and interests of all ethnic groups.</p> <p>Regional ethnic autonomy is the Party's core policy in solving China's ethnic problem. The unity and struggle of all ethnic groups for common prosperity and development is the theme of ethnic work at the present stage.</p> <p>Accelerating the economic and social development of ethnic minorities and ethnic regions is the main task of ethnic work at the present stage and the main way to solve ethnic problems in China (Wang Xiaodong, LI Xiang & Wang Zhou, 2021).</p>

<p>Attitudes of political parties towards inter-ethnic relations</p>	<p>"Unity in diversity", "We are different, we are equal" - these are Kazakhstan's aspirations and stated goals for developing ethnic relations. Kazakhstan regulates interethnic relations and processes in its national policy on the basis of the legal framework, including the Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan, relevant bodies and institutions operating at the level of central, regional and local authorities. Article 14 of the Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan guarantees that "Everyone shall be equal before the law and court. No one shall be subject to any discrimination for reasons of origin, social, property status, occupation, sex, race, nationality, language, attitude towards religion, convictions, place of residence or any other circumstances". Article 19 states that "Everyone shall have the right to use his native language and culture, to freely choose the language of communication, education, instruction and creative activities" (Constitution, 1995). Accordingly, representatives of all nationalities and ethnic groups living in the territory of the Republic enjoy the same rights without discrimination. In addition, in the ruling party's constitution, the party's task of building multi-ethnic relations is clearly defined as - "promoting and strengthening inter-ethnic and inter-faith harmony and social stability" (Charter, 2022). Parties treat every citizen equally and openly, "to provide every citizen with the opportunity to become familiar with the Party's documents, decisions and sources of information that affect their rights and interests."</p>	<p>"The community of the Chinese nation" is a new concept for the CPC in its understanding and consideration of ethnic relations. This concept marks a new theoretical level in the understanding and consideration of ethnic relations of CPC, it is modern in nature, consistent with the "a community with a shared future for mankind". "The community of the Chinese nation" is characterized by unity of destiny and unity of interests. Theoretically, it originates from the thought of "Great Unification" in traditional Chinese culture, but it also deeply contains the Marxist community theory and develops from the idea of the pluralistic unity of the Chinese nation. The Constitution of the Communist Party of China defines the relationship between the CPC and members of all ethnic groups as follows: "The Communist Party of China is the leadership core for the cause of socialism with Chinese characteristics," "The CPC led the Chinese people of all ethnic groups..." "The CPC leads and unites the people of all ethnic groups throughout the country..." "The CPC supports and develops socialist interethnic relations of equality, unity, mutual assistance and harmony," "The CPC is united with the workers, peasants and intellectuals of all ethnic groups in the country" support the reunification of the motherland and are committed to the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation (Constitution, 2022).</p>
<p>Historical activities</p>	<p>The ruling party of Kazakhstan and the Government pursue three important principles of the policy of national harmony. The national policy of the state, first of all, protects human rights and does not allow infringement of the rights of small ethnic groups. The strategic approach of national policy is to use constructive methods for resolving inter-ethnic conflicts and developing the country's economy in the interests of all nationalities living on the territory of the state. The legal status and rights of small ethnic groups in the state are guaranteed by all legal means (Aiguly Yimin, 2010). The Republic of Kazakhstan has ratified over 180 fundamental international normative legal acts in the field of regulation of interethnic and interfaith relations.</p>	<p>In the socialist revolution and construction stage, the CPC consolidated the political foundation for the construction of the Chinese national community by building institutions, ensured the realization of the internal rights of community members through policies, and laid the foundation for understanding the multi-ethnic situation through ethnic identification. In the new period of reform, opening up and socialist modernization, the CPC studies the theory and practice of building the Chinese national community at three levels: the macroscopic ideological value system, the mesoscopic political system and the microscopic action system (Wang Xing, 2020), focusing on economic development, and shaping the interconnection of economic interests of the Chinese nation.</p>

Practices	<p>Kazakhstan's model of social concord and national unity.</p> <p>Kazakhstan's model is based on the consolidating principle of "Unity through diversity". The state's targeted policy of supporting ethnic languages and cultures contributes to the preservation and multiplication of cultural diversity.</p> <p>The first stage (from 1989 to 1995). It is characterized from the beginning of the creation of ethno-cultural associations to the beginning of legislative and institutionalization of the Kazakh model as a result of the adoption of the 1995 Constitution and the creation of the Assembly of the People of Kazakhstan.</p> <p>The second stage (from 1995 to 2002). The parameters of Kazakhstani identity were defined. Based on the Concept of Forming the State Identity of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the consolidation of Kazakh society around the Kazakh people has been ensured. A principled consensus has been reached in society on the refusal to politicize ethnic and confessional relations.</p> <p>The third stage (from 2002 to 2007). It includes policies on formation of the Kazakhstani model of interethnic tolerance. A number of program documents were developed and adopted - the Strategy of the Assembly of the People of Kazakhstan until 2011, the State Program for the development and functioning of languages, the Concept "Ideological consolidation of society - as a condition for the progress of Kazakhstan". From 2006 to 2008, the Program for Improving Kazakhstan's Model of Interethnic and Interfaith concord was implemented.</p> <p>The fourth stage began in 2007. It is characterized by the integration of Kazakh society into a unified nation, the transition of the state national policy to a policy of strengthening the national unity of the people of Kazakhstan. (Assembly of People of Kazakhstan, 2024)</p> <p>The Assembly of the People of Kazakhstan (APK) plays a crucial role in the formation of a unique model of all-Kazakhstan unity. The main task is to implement the state national policy, ensure social and political stability in the Republic of Kazakhstan and increase the effectiveness of interaction between state and civil society institutions in the sphere of inter-ethnic relations.</p> <p>Case from practice:</p> <p>2023 in the House of Friendship in Astana at the XXXII session of the the Assembly of people of Kazakhstan Deputy Chairman Marat Azilkhonov and Executive Secretary of the party "Amanat" Elnur Beisenbaev signed a Memorandum of Mutual Cooperation.</p> <p>The purpose of this Memorandum is to ensure interaction and cooperation between the two sides on issues of strengthening social harmony and national unity.</p>	<p>After the founding of the new China, the CPC formulated guidelines and policies on ethnic work, the main elements of which were ethnic equality, ethnic unity, regional ethnic autonomy and common prosperity for all ethnic groups.</p> <p>Ethnic equality. The Constitution of the People's Republic of China (PRC) states that "All ethnic groups in the People's Republic of China are equal" (Chapter I, Article 4) (Constitution, 2018). In accordance with the spirit of this principle, the PRC Law on Regional Ethnic Autonomy and other laws and regulations contain specific and clear provisions on ethnic equality.</p> <p>The equality of all nationalities has three meanings: firstly, all nationalities are equal in political status, regardless of population size, length of history, size of the territory in which they live, degree of economic development, and whether they share the same language, script, religious beliefs and customs; secondly, all nationalities are equal not only politically and legally, but also in all spheres of economic, cultural and social life; and thirdly, citizens of all nationalities are equal before the law, enjoy the same rights and bear the same responsibilities.</p> <p>The principle of equality of nationalities is enshrined in the specific provisions of the Election Law of the National People's Congress and Local People's Congresses of the People's Republic of China, the Regulations on Religious Affairs, the Civil Procedure Law of the People's Republic of China and other documents.</p> <p>National unity. Xi Jinping, as the leader of the Chinese state and the CPC, has repeatedly pointed out the importance of the unity of all ethnic groups and has constantly linked the unity of all ethnic groups with the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation.</p> <p>"The realization of the Chinese Dream must unite the strength of China. This strength is the strength of the great unity of the Chinese people of all ethnic groups" (Xi Jinping, 2014).</p> <p>"To achieve the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation, we must strengthen the great unity of the people of all ethnic groups in the country and resolutely safeguard the unity of the motherland and social harmony and stability" (Xi Jinping, 2016).</p> <p>"Unity is strength, unity is the way forward, and a divided country cannot develop and progress" (Xi Jinping, 2018).</p> <p>"The closeness of people of all ethnic groups to each other is the fundamental guarantee of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation" (Xi Jinping, 2019).</p> <p>The system of regional ethnic autonomy</p> <p>Strengthening national unity is fundamentally about respecting and improving the system of regional ethnic autonomy.</p> <p>The General Program of the Chinese People's Political Consultative Conference, which it adopted in 1949 and acted as a provisional constitution, established regional ethnic autonomy as the basic policy of the new China. In 1952, the</p>
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	<p>In his speech, Marat Azilkhanov noted that “It is no coincidence that the Head of State emphasized that the Assembly played an important role in the political modernization of the country, contributed to the expansion of public support for reforms, and the involvement of all ethnic groups in solving strategic tasks of the state’s development.”</p> <p>“The activities of the Assembly of people of Kazakhstan, its public structures and ethnocultural associations are concentrated on work on a wide range of issues that concern society, building and strengthening various platforms for interethnic communication, information and ideological work. "(APK, 2023)</p> <p>During 2023 and 2024, such memorandums of cooperation have been signed with all registered political parties in Kazakhstan.</p>	<p>Central People's Government promulgated the “Implementation Outline of Regional Autonomy of Ethnic Minorities in the People's Republic of China”, containing clear provisions on important issues such as the establishment of national autonomous regions, the composition of self-governing bodies and the autonomy rights of self-governing. The Constitution adopted by the National People's Congress in 1954 enshrined this system as a basic law, and it has been consistently applied.</p> <p>In 1984, based on the synthesis of the historical experience of regional ethnic autonomies, the Law on Regional Ethnic Autonomy was promulgated, realizing the trinity of policy, system and law in China's regional ethnic autonomy.</p> <p>The Law on Regional Ethnic Autonomy is the basic law for the implementation of the constitutional system of regional ethnic autonomy, regulating the relationship between the central government and the regional ethnic autonomous areas, as well as the relationship between different ethnic groups in the ethnic autonomous regions.</p>
<p>Views of other major political parties</p>	<p>Party pluralism in Kazakhstan tends to support the building of inter-ethnic relations and the strengthening of national concord, advocating equality, respect and community among all ethnic groups to promote stability, consolidation and democratic development of the country.</p>	<p>China's other democratic parties share a similar basic position with the CPC on building a multi-ethnic state, advocating ethnic equality, unity, autonomy and shared prosperity. Although these democratic parties occupy a relatively weak position in China's political system, they still play a role in working with ethnic groups and provide suggestions and advice to national policy-making.</p>

Conclusions

The analysis carried out by the authors showed the general and special in the national policies of Kazakhstan and China, the structure and content of modern challenges to the development of interethnic relations in multi-ethnic states.

Firstly, in terms of policy orientation, the CPC's ethnic policy aims at national unity, equality and common prosperity, emphasizing exchanges, mutual penetration and the common development of all ethnic groups. The harmonious coexistence of ethnic groups is promoted through measures such as regional autonomy and development policies for the ethnic regions.

Kazakhstan pursues similar policies, emphasizing equality and concord among ethnic groups, involving them in political decision-making.

Secondly, although countries such as China and Kazakhstan have adopted a series of measures to promote economic development in ethnic minority areas under the policy of protecting diversity that is prioritized by political parties, in fact the problem of uneven economic development still exists. Some ethnic minority areas still face problems such as poverty and inadequate infrastructure, which may exacerbate popular discontent, social and inter-ethnic tensions.

Thirdly, at the level of autonomy and unity, China has pursued a policy of regional autonomy, establishing five autonomous regions and a number of autonomous prefectures and counties, giving ethnic minorities more

autonomy rights to meet their historical, cultural and religious needs.

Kazakhstan also encourages smaller ethnic groups within the structure of the unified nation of Kazakhstan to play a more significant role in their compactly living ethnic groups in the regions. Today in the structure of the people of Kazakhstan there are representatives of more than 100 ethnic groups.

Fourthly, in order to more effectively manage internal ethnic relations, promote incentives for harmonious and orderly development in strengthening inter-ethnic relations, and to reduce potential ethnic tensions, special bodies have been created in both countries at the state and civil levels for ethnic affairs. In China, National Ethnic Affairs Commission of the People's Republic of China coordinates overall national policy, ensuring ethnic diversity, rights and guarantees for ethnic groups within the state. At all levels, from central to local, a clearly structured organizational system has been formed, which plays an important role in promoting and coordinating the political rights of China's ethnic minorities, their economic development, the development and progress of their cultural and social causes, and also has a significant influence on the formulation, the implementation and execution of the ethnic policy of the Party and the state. This is closely related to the multi-ethnic history and specific realities and characteristics of China.

In Kazakhstan, despite the development of state and political governance, the coordination of institutional development in the sphere of interethnic relations (the Secretariat of the Assembly of the People of Kazakhstan functions in the structure of the Executive Office of the President, the Committee for the Development of Interethnic Relations, the Republican State Institution "Kogamdyk Kelisim" and Institute of Applied Ethnopolitical Research functions within the structure of the Ministry of Culture and Information of the Republic of Kazakhstan), socio-political structures and civil society institutions still attach great importance to strengthening social harmony and national unity. A key role in strengthening the stable development of Kazakhstan and national identity is played by the Assembly of the People of Kazakhstan (APK, since March 1, 1995), which united more than 1000 ethnocultural associations, Councils of Mothers and Elders, youth organizations, the Association of Departments of the APK "Shanyrak" and the scientific and expert community.

Fifthly, challenges and responses. China faces uneven development of ethnic regions, conflicts between preserving ethnic culture and modernization, and the ideology of ethnic separatism in some regions, so it needs to take additional measures to strengthen national unity. Kazakhstan faces similar problems, especially in finding a balance between ethnic and national identities, as well as in intra-ethnic relations, which sometimes develop in a latent state.

The general and special in the national models of the two countries show the possibilities and mechanisms for the development of ethnopolitics, demonstrate experience tested by the practice of legislative and socio-political participation in the regulation and management of this sphere in multi-ethnic states.

National unity is one of the important factors contributing to social development and progress. Ethnic groups will be able to unite as one and work together for the development and prosperity of the country, in creating a more favorable social environment to ensure economic, cultural, scientific and technological development.

Taken together, these measures aim to create an inclusive political environment that ensures equal participation of all ethnic groups in government. It is important to note that there may be challenges and opportunities for improvement when implementing these measures. However, these measures reflect the efforts and aspirations of both governments for political modernization in multi-ethnic governance.

The analysis of the relationship between political parties and inter-ethnic integration in the governance of representative multi-ethnic states shows that inter-ethnic political integration in multi-ethnic states is carried out mainly through the ruling parties, whose activities in this area are supported by the population.

The existing challenges in strengthening inter-ethnic relations, identified on the basis of the analysis, such as uneven economic development in ethnic areas, relative lagging behind in education and infrastructure development, problems of formation of national identity, preservation of ethnic cultures, historical memory,

etc. also have common and special features, taking into account the complexities of the modern world order.

However, although with the direct role of political parties it has a huge reserve for the democratic development of inter-ethnic relations and the formation of ethno-management, the most important tool of "soft power" of public diplomacy in both inter-country and internal political cooperation and interaction is not always fully used.

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